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Research

Article

**ANALYSIS OF GENDER DISPARITY IN-HOSPITAL
COMPLICATIONS AFTER PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY
INTERVENTION (PCI) OF CULPRIT VESSEL FOR ACUTE
CORONARY SYNDROME (ACS)****Dr Muhammad Muhboob Khan¹, Dr Zeeshan Khalid¹, Dr Ashiq Hussain¹**
¹Nishtar Hospital, Multan**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine the frequency of male and female undergoing PCI of Culprit Vessel and gender based comparison of in-hospital post PCI complications in these patients. **Study Design:** This descriptive case series study was conducted at Nishtar hospital, Multan during June 2019 to January 2020. It was non-probability purposive sampling. All the baseline procedural and biochemical characteristics recorded. Frequency of males and females undergoing PCI of Culprit Vessel during this duration was calculated then these patients were evaluated for Post PCI Complications. **Results:** Out of total 135 patients undergoing Culprit vessel PCI male 75 (55.55%) were more as compare to female 60(44.44%). Post PCI Complications were significantly higher in females as compare to males. i.e hematoma 35(31.81%) in female as compare to 10(9.09%) in males. MI female 15(13.63%) males 5(4.54%), Death females 2 (3.6%) males 1(1.8%) and CABG 0 (0%) in both males and females. **Conclusion:** This study shows that in Pakistan PCI of Culprit vessel is more in males as compare to females and females are at increased risk of post PCI complications i.e Vascular complications and Post PCI MI and death but emergency CABG after PCI is the same in both genders.

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INTRODUCTION:

Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI) is the most common interventional procedure used for Coronary revascularization. The number of PCI is increasing with the passage of time due to increased awareness and improved outcomes compared to fibrinolytic therapy for coronary artery disease (CAD)¹. Meta- analyses of randomized clinical trials have reported that primary PCI is more cost effective compared to fibrinolytic and reduces the incidence of death, reinfarction and stroke. Furthermore in stable patients and in patients with multivessel disease, PCI has become the preferred procedure in the united states with declining mortality in patients undergoing multivessel PCI². PCI also has got many complications like other interventions i.e Death, myocardial infarction (MI), emergency CABG or re do PCI, stroke, contrast induced nephropathy (CIN) Vascular complications before intervention³. GpIIb/IIIa inhibitors have reduced the mortality by 20% over 6-12 months in unstable angina and non-ST elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI). PCI has not shown any mortality benefit in stable angina. Ischemic heart disease (IHD) is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in women. Sex based differences has been area of active investigation over the past two decades⁴. Symptoms of females appear at elder age as compare to male, however the symptoms of females are atypical as compare to males. The diagnosis is more difficult in females and prognosis is less favorable⁵.

OBJECTIVE

1. To determine the frequency of male and female undergoing PCI of culprit vessel.
2. To compare in-hospital post PCI complications of culprit vessel between male and female.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This descriptive case series study was conducted at Nishtar hospital, Multan during June 2019 to January 2020. It was non-probability purposive sampling. A total of 135 PCI of culprit vessels were done. All the baseline procedural and biochemical characteristics recorded. Frequency of males and females undergoing PCI of Culprit Vessel during this duration was calculated then these patients were evaluated for Post PCI Complications.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Previous PCI or CABG
2. Left main Stem (LMS) PCI

DATA COLLECTION:

These patients were admitted to hospital with ACS. These patients received Primary, Rescue and facilitated PCI. 110 patients (55 males and 55 females) out of these 135 patients were selected. Written consent was taken before starting the study protocol. Detail History with demographic features was taken and patients were divided in two groups on the basis of gender. Risk factors were also stratified i.e

- Diabetes Mellitus (fasting blood sugar >126 mg/dl and Random >200 mg/dl)
- Hypertension (sustained elevation in blood pressure of >140/80 or previous history) and smoking.

DATA ANALYSIS

All data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS (statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 12 for window. Continuous (Age, BMI) and Categorical variables (Gender, procedural complications i.e CIN, Hematoma, MI. etc), were presented as mean \pm standard deviation and frequency/percentages respectively. Risk factors for IHD i.e diabetes mellitus and hypertension, smoking and hyper lipedimia are presented as frequency tables.

RESULTS:

A total of 135 angioplasties of culprit vessel were done. Males were more in number as compared to females. i.e 75 males (55.55%) and 60 females (44.44%). Out of these 110 patients (55 males and 55 females) were selected for this study. These patients were fulfilling the Inclusion and exclusion criteria. Baseline characteristics of the patients who underwent PCI are shown below in table 1. Mean age of the male patients was 49.8 ± 9.60 while that of female patients was 52.1 ± 8.91 .

Out of 525 male patients who underwent PCI, 21% of the patients were diabetics. Hypertension was present in 46% of the male patients. Among the female patients the incidence of diabetes and hypertension was 29% and 53% respectively. The mean body mass index (BMI) of female patients was also higher than the male patients i.e 30.2 vs 28.6 respectively.

TABLE 1. Base line characteristics

Variable	Male	Female
Age, years	49.8 \pm 9.60	52.1 \pm 8.91
Diabetes Mellitus	25.45% (14)	32.72% (18)
Hypertension	50.90% (28)	56.36% (31)

TABLE 2. This table below shows the comparison of indications for percutaneous Intervention between males and females.**TABLE 2.Indications for PCI**

	Male(55)	Female(55)
Acute Myocardial Infarction (primary)	14.54%(8)	5.45%(3)
Acute Myocardial Infarction(rescue)	5.45%(3)	3.63%(2)
Acute Myocardial Infarction (elective)	41.81%(23)	56.36(31)
NSTEMI	27.27%(15)	25.45%(14)
Unstable Angina	10.90%(6)	9.09%(5)

DISCUSSION:

Main function of heart is to provide circulatory needs of the body. Heart also need its own metabolic requirements. These requirements are met through the coronary blood flow. Heart needs aerobic metabolism, there is limited capacity of heart to tolerate anaerobic metabolism. Heart has a unique mechanism of oxygen extraction. Under basal condition it extract high degree of oxygen so that it can adjust a changing oxygen needs by only a small increment in oxygen extraction⁸. There is more coronary blood flow if there's more need of oxygen to the cardiac muscle. To measure the oxygen consumption by cardiac muscle certain studies have been done on animals⁹. It is very difficult to calculate the mean myocardial oxygen consumptions (MVO₂) there is laboratory data that can be used to measure MVO₂. To meet the bad time heart has sufficient reservoir of oxygen¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is the total obstruction of the artery usually at the site of access requiring surgical repair. Conclusion is defined as total obstruction of blood vessel usually due to the thrombus formation dissection or other mechanisms usually at the site of access of plaque pulse or Doppler signal and associated with sign and symptoms of an ischemic limb requiring surgical intervention.

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